

Mini Dreams: Are You Dreaming?

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1. Description

The artist couldn't comprehend the source of the unknown voice. The question still remaining—who is he? The artist didn't recognize the voice. Still, he is wondering. When he turned to look at the man who questioned the artist - 'Excuse me?' The artist turned towards the source of the voice and he realized that he wasn't able to focus on the man's face, but he knew it was there. The artist eagerly wanted to see his face. The artist knew what it was, even though the artist couldn't make it out.

The organism spoke to the artist again: 'You are dreaming, aren't you? You made this?' The artist watched everywhere at the boardwalk they were standing on. People were passing by us, unconcerned with their conversation. The voice came again very close and clearer, we know that you have been contacted by a certain individual. A man who calls himself Mono. Please see the figure of Mono in Figure 1. Whatever you think you know about this man is irrelevant. The matter of fact is that the Mono is responsible for acts of dream terrorism in more countries than any other man in the world. He is considered by many authorities to be the most dangerous man alive.

Figure 1. The Mono (character) is designed and depicted based on a mini dream by the author.

The author doesn't understand why he is having this conversation and who is this man standing against the white bright light. He came closer and said the author's colleagues believe that the author is wasting his time with colleagues but he believes colleagues want to do the right thing. It is obvious that the author and his colleagues are intelligent men who are interested in living in this dream.

Mono also said –

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Are you still dreaming?

So, what's it feels like when you go diving?

Didn't you go through underwater training?

I 'am not talking about doing it in a damned pool.

Authors feel fear, anxiety, loneliness, and darkness underwater, and perhaps, even hope.

Hope? In the darkness of the sea? As the author suddenly float up towards the water surface.

The author almost felt, as if, he could change the dream into something else. That is why the character designer (author) believe they are ready to put their past mistakes behind them and get on with their life. Suddenly, the phone rang and he looked at it, and, he saw his father was calling. Then, he realized that “he is no more, how can he? The author was struggling to find out whether it is real or he is still dreaming. He did everything that he remembers, pinched himself, blinked his eyes, and slapped his face but he still heard the same voice that kept his conversation going. The author tried to reach closer to that voice but he couldn't; Somehow the distance was the same as before, the voice asked “We are willing to wipe the slate clean to give you a fresh start. Are you in?

The Mono is a hypothetical character derived and depicted from a mini dream of the author during a scary night of spring in 2021. This character can be utilized as a science fiction character like the alien in Star Wars (Lucas, Hales, Duursema, Gilroy, and Kryssing, 2002; Lucas and Wheatley, 2005) or Guardians of the Galaxy (Bendis, 2013; Huber, 2015), etc. The same character can also be utilized in action or horror games.

References

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